

A Study on Customer Satisfaction on Digital Marketing

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ABSTRACT

During different time era's different methods of communications has developed and changed the everyday life. Social media has become the way of communication in the 21st-century, enabling us to express our thoughts, ideas and feelings in a complete new way. This way of communication have also had a huge impact on corporations, where they have realized that without a proper plan and social media strategy they have no chance to stand out in the rapidly changing digital space. To ensure a successful presence on social media the companies need to take different marketing theories into consideration so that they can boost their brand in diverse aspects. If this can be combined with innovative ways of consumer interaction the companies have a good chance to take the lead in social media marketing.

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INTRODUCTION:

This internship report has been prepared as a requirement for the completion of the Master of Business Administration (MBA) program of BRAC University. After the completion of 60 credits of MBA program, I started my internship program at my workplace, NRB Bazaar under content and Digital Marketing department. My organizational line manager was Mr. Shahnewaz Reza Mansur, Assistant Manager, Content & Digital Marketing, NRB Bazaar. Given a choice one was allowed to choose the field in which I was interested. As my interest and curiosity was in online or digital marketing, I choose to work with a startup company where I work. NRB Bazaar is a 2 years old global based e-commerce company, the industry which has effected radical changes in the market. I chose digital marketing because it is a blooming method, the growth of digital marketing is tremendous and expected to grow more. Every industry is affected by the advances of digital marketing, especially e-commerce sector. Digital marketing is one of the most popular and effective marketing method in this techno savvy world in terms of cost and customer engagement. Due to this fall internship, I have learned many aspects of digital marketing including business development process, content writing, and social media management.

REVIEW OF LITERATURE:

Alireza Mohammadpour et.al (2016) This study aims to evaluate the effect of social media marketing on online shopping of customers based on mediating role of value capital, relational capital and brand capital by path analysis method. 169 students from Tehran University were selected

to collect the data. The students filled out the questionnaire of social media marketing, value capital, relational capital, brand capital and e-shopping of customers. From the study the researcher concluded, social media marketing has indirectly positive and significant impact on e-shopping customers via value capital, relational capital and brand capital.

Mei-Ying Wu & Li-Hsia Tseng "their study attempt to know about the differences in perception of experiential marketing, customer satisfaction, and customer satisfaction across demographic variables, the relationship among experiential marketing, customer satisfaction, and customer loyalty, and applicability of experiential marketing in the online retailing industry For this study questionnaire has been collected among" According to the descriptive statistics of the sample, the sample comprised mainly female respondents. Most of the respondents were aged between 20-39, married, and living in northern cities of Taiwan strategic experiential modules, experiential marketing, customer satisfaction, customer loyalty where used as statistical tool. The result found that " This finding suggests that lativ should be more committed to creating experiences for customers so as to indirectly enhance their satisfaction. Experiential marketing has a positive relation with customer loyalty (H3). Results showed that experiential marketing was positively related to customer loyalty

Shockley-Zalabak (2006) Change will, and must happen. It is in the best interest of organizations to pursue continuous

change and proactively design strategies for change. Organizational change takes both planning and management (Shockley-Zalabak, 2006). Those willing to accept and plan changes will bury organizations that ignore this important business dynamic. Changes occur everywhere around us. Most organizations have created a system or group to plan for continuous improvement and change. Upon accepting the need to anticipate continuous change, every organization must then determine its own method of dealing with the modifications. Shockley-Zalabak (2006) stated, "how change is handled, the amount of change, who decides what to change, and a host of other issues are part of the pervasive pace of change that almost all of us experience"

(Zorn, Page & Cheney, 2000) In the increasing globalization of our world, organizational environments are constantly under rapid change and unpredictability. Globalization has increased competition, technological development and customer demand. Organizations must maintain a sense of flexibility, ensuring quick adaptation to the challenges they are facing. The most common changes that modern organizations undergo are relatively similar. They are changes in programs focused on customer service, organizational quality, and teamwork. Organizations in all sectors today tend to mimic one another's actions of change to remain competitive, making it critical for organizational innovation, new ideas, and practices vital to success (Zorn, Page & Cheney, 2000). Snow College is no exception in the need to change and continually adapt to new marketing practices.

(Nohria, Joyce, & Robertson, 2003) It is necessary to continually monitor the market of any particular organization and its needs. A constant observation of the market will ensure the elimination of excess waste, while increasing productivity. Studies have noted the importance of having "talented employees, innovation, leadership, and mergers and partnership," (Nohria, Joyce, & Robertson, 2003, p. 213) in order to make certain efficient change and adaptation to the ever-changing market. Nohria, Joyce, & Robertson (2003) also discuss the need to look outside in, as a resource to decision making. Listen to employees, customers, partners, and investors

Research Methodology:

Primary Data - The Primary data were collected using self-Administered questionnaire.

Secondary Data- The Secondary data were collected from the research Papers and articles published in different Journals.

OBJECTIVES ON THE STUDY;

Utilize Social Media and other technology to increase Snow College enrollment. Begin enrollment growth by building an inquiry pool of 5,500 – 8,500 students then convert these inquiries into 1,500 – 2,500 admitted students. Based on several years records we expect from these admits, that 50 percent or 750 – 1,250 will enroll. The following is a list of activities and programs that we will complete this year to increase precious number. Social media and other technology will be utilized to bring admitted numbers from 1,500-2,500 students to 2,000-3,000 students. Then increasing the student yield form 50 percent to 60 percent. To meet our objective a strategic plan of social media and other technology will assist to increase the numbers to the desired outcomes

SAMPLING:

To Study the impact of Digital Marketing on various parameters, A Structured questionnaire for collecting primary data. Primary data was collected from 100 respondents. Respondents are selected from Mumbai District, Maharashtra. Primary data in structured format was collected via direct questioning to respondents, which is direct through survey method. Sample Size for this study is 100 who are purchasing products or services through digital channel. The data was analyzed and hypothesis is tested with Statistical tool like chi-square test

TOOLS:

Percentage analysis is the tool used to analyze the data .the following tools will be considered analysis

- Percentage analysis
- Chi square

PERCENTAGE ANALYSIS:

1. INTERNET MEDIUMS MOSTLY USED IN KOSOVO:

TABLE 1

Face book	735 (Almost 800,000 users)
Email	65%
Skype	65%
YouTube	43%

Source: STIKK - Kosovo Association of Information and Communication Technology

Moreover, the same study shows that 800,000 user of internet users in Kosovo use internet to communicate with friends and relatives outside Kosovo. So, it is a very active market and the opportunities for this market to be exploited in terms of marketing are plenty.

2. TYPE OF SOCIAL MEDIA USED FOR DIGITAL MARKETING:

TABLE 2

S. No	Social media	Frequency	Percentage
1	Face book	114	76.0
2	Instagram	28	18.7
3	Twitter	2	1.3
4	Pinterest	3	2.0
5	Linkedin	3	2.0
	Total	150	100.0

From the above table, it is inferred that 76% of respondents use Facebook for Digital marketing, 1.3% of the respondents use Twitter for Digital marketing.

3. PREFERENCE TO GET THE INFORMATION

TABLE 3

S. No	Options	Frequency	Percentage
1	Social media	68	45.3
2	Emails	48	32.0
3	Advertisements	16	10.7
4	Website	9	6.0
5	Stores	1	.7
6	Pamphlets	8	5.3
	Total	150	100.0

From the above table, it is inferred that 45.3% of the respondents prefer social media to get the information, 0.7% of the respondents prefer stores to get the information

4. FREQUENCY OF USING SOCIAL MEDIA

TABLE 4

S. No	Options	Frequency	Percentage
1	Daily	127	84.7
2	Once in a week	12	8.0
3	Seldom	11	7.3
	Total	150	100.0

From the above table, it is inferred that 84.7% of the respondents use social media daily, 7.3% of the respondents use social media seldom

CHI SQUARE:

1. Association between Age of the Respondents and Time Spend on Social Media to Purchase Online Products. Chi- Square:

TABLE 1

	Value	Df	Asymptotic Significance (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	43.335	12	.000
Likelihood Ratio	46.397	12	.000
Linear-by-Linear Association	18.370	1	.000
N of Valid Cases	149		

H0 - There is no significant relationship between age of the respondents and time spend on social media to purchase online products.

H1 - There is significant relationship between age of the respondents and time spend on social media to purchase online products

2. ASSOCIATION BETWEEN THE TIME PERIOD OF USING DIGITAL MARKETING AND OCCUPATION OF THE RESPONDENTS ONE WAY ANOVA:

TABLE 2

	Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	.Sig
Between Groups	.874	2	.437	.326	.722
Within Group	196.999	147	1.340		
Total	197.873	149			

H0 - There is no significant relationship between the time period of using digital marketing and occupation of the respondents.

H1 - There is significant relationship between the time period of using digital marketing and occupation of the respondents

3. ASSOCIATION BETWEEN MONTHLY INCOME AND MONEY SPEND ON DIGITAL MARKETING:

TABLE 3

	Money Spend on Digital Marketing
Kruskal-Wallis H	20.665
Df	3
Asymp. Sig	.000

H0 - There is no significant relationship between monthly income and money spend on digital marketing.

H1 - There is significant relationship between the monthly income and money spend on digital marketing

DATA ANALYSIS:

The students who responded to the survey were a mix of Undergraduate and postgraduate students:

UG - Russian Politics/Facebook - 100% daily/weekly usage

The data reveals that awareness and usage of social media were generally high. 70% used resource at least once. Daily usage significantly higher for Facebook, while Twitter more than twice as likely to have never been used

FINDING:

To quickly summarize the advantages of the digital marketing as seen from the point of view of the user as well as the marketer. These findings are an outcome from the experience of the researchers at Digitally Inspired Media. Also, they are from the view point of the organization and its client's customers. The best example of giving control of content is the My Yahoo!! service offered by the Internet giant, Yahoo Inc. It gives the user the choice of content for various topics ranging from news to stock options to entertainment to sports and just about everything

CONCLUSION:

By completing this report I have learned a lot that will help enrich my knowledge and experience. Before starting my internship I was very anxious and nervous about the new department to work with and how I was going to fit into it. But I was glad to be able to join a team that has ingrained positivity and friendliness. Each and every one that I have

worked with in NRB Bazaar has helped me fit into the corporate environment so well that I have started feeling a certain loyalty to this organization. Overall experience that I have got from this internship program would be an unforgettable experience and this would be working as a direction to my future career. I have done major in Marketing and I had to work in the content and digital marketing department of NRB Bazaar and this has increased my knowledge level in the digital marketing sector. In this report I mainly discussed the rising trends of e-commerce business as well as the impact of Digital marketing in this essential industries that influence the current economy of Bangladesh. Moreover, some of the recent trend in digital marketing is included as well.

SUGGESTIONS:

A total of 119 students completed the survey. All of the students were in their last month of high school or had finished in previous years. Eighty-three parents finished the survey. Similar to other studies from the literature review that asked students directly if and how they used social media tools for communicating or seeking information about colleges, students did not acknowledge social media as a tool they used. Questions on seeking information about colleges referred to the three largest social media sites as cited from various sources in the literature review: Facebook, YouTube and Twitter. Each of the three social media tools ranked lower than college websites, and not just a little bit lower. Both from the student and parents perspective these social media platforms appear to have little to no value when seeking information about colleges.

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